

CLINICAL AND PATHOLOGICAL SYMPTOMS OF STOMACH ULCER AND MEASURES FOR ITS PREVENTION

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Abstract: In today's world, gastric ulcer disease is serious problem for both young and old. Because this disease is caused by bad eating habits of a person. What is a stomach ulcer, how does it appear, what are the measures to prevent it, and how can it be treated. You will find answers and remedies to these questions in this article.

Key words: Stomach ulcer, Occurrence, Development, Preventive measures, Prophylaxis, Treatment methods.

The purpose of the topic: prevention of the spread of stomach ulcer diseases and development of methods of its treatment.

The main part of the topic: How does a stomach ulcer appear? Hydrochloric acid and enzymes are two aggressive factors that affect the mucous membrane of the stomach. These substances have special role in the digestion of food products that have entered the stomach. In order for these substances not to damage the mucous membrane, a special mucus is secreted in the mucous membrane as a defense mechanism. This defensive mechanism consists of bicarbonates.

Excessive secretion of aggressive factors and decrease in protective function leads to damage of the mucous membrane. Firstly, erosion will appear, then an ulcer can be seen. Acidic juice from the stomach passes into the duodenum and the inflammatory process begins (duodenitis), erosion and ulcer will develop gradually. Helicobacter pylori plays the biggest role in the origin of the disease.

In the chronic form of ulcer disease, the symptoms of the disease develop from time to time and periods of remission are different. An attack usually occurs after physical and mental stress, when the diet is disturbed, and as a result of the influence of harmful habits. The disease often occurs in men. In addition, it is necessary to emphasize that ulcer disease occurs in middle-aged people and causes social and economic problems.

Long-term use of certain drugs. Taking nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs in particular causes damage to the mucous membrane wall.

In addition to the above reasons, stress, physical exertion, drinking alcohol, smoking tobacco products, the constant presence of bitter, spicy, fried, smoked products in the diet, and the violation of the diet also play an important role in the development of the disease.

SYMPTOMS OBSERVED IN STOMACH ULCER DISEASE

Clinical symptoms of the disease usually appear in a typical form and do not cause difficulties in diagnosing the disease. One of the main clinical symptoms is pain. Pain in ulcer diseases usually occurs on an empty stomach or 2-3 hours after eating.

If an ulcer appears in the cardiac part of the stomach, the pain appears in the area near the solar system, 20 minutes after eating. The pain can also spread upwards, i.e. To the chest. This often makes it difficult to diagnose stomach ulcers and heart attacks. If the wound is located in the cardiac part, the pain does not appear after physical exertion.

A symptom of a pyloric ulcer is long-lasting pain. Sometimes the duration of pain can last from 40 minutes to 1 hour. The pain usually starts 40-60 minutes after eating. It usually appears at night. In addition, patients may experience dyspeptic syndromes - nausea, vomiting, weakness, abdominal pain. In 5-10% of cases, the wound in this area leads to negative complications (penetration, bleeding, perforation, stenosis).

In 10-15% of cases, the ulcer occurs in the antral part of the stomach. Severe pain is usually manifested at night, in the area under the left rib. The pain lasts until the food mass in the stomach cavity is digested and broken down. If the ulcer develops in the large curvature of the stomach, it can lead to serious complications, this condition often occurs in elderly people, and the diagnosis of such ulcers is very difficult.

Duodenal ulcers usually occur in people under 40 years of age. Hereditary predisposition plays a big role in the occurrence of the disease. In the disease, the pain syndrome appears 1.5-2 hours after eating, while dyspeptic symptoms are rarely observed, patients complain of constipation.

TREATMENT OF STOMACH ULCER DISEASE

Patients are advised to diet, avoid bad habits, avoid stressful situations and follow a strict daily schedule. Treatment procedures are usually carried out for 14 days. Individual treatment is prescribed for each patient, taking into account the patient's condition, age, profession and concomitant diseases. Wound disease is a serious disease, and if it is not treated on time, it can lead to complications and even death.

Medical treatment includes:

- Antibacterial drugs - to eliminate H. pylori in the body;
- Antacid drugs - in order to reduce gastric juice secretion;
- Proton pump inhibitors - affect the secretion of hydrochloric acid and reduce its "aggressiveness";
- H2-histamine blockers - reduce the "aggressiveness" of gastric juice;
- Spasmolytics - prescribed as a symptomatic treatment during pain.
- It is necessary to take the prescribed medicines on time and during the prescribed period.

The reduction of symptoms does not mean that you should stop taking the drugs.

SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ULCER DISEASE (REMOVAL OF ULCER)

Surgery can be planned or urgently performed in case of long-term ineffectiveness of conservative treatment and non-healing of the wound. Urgent operative treatment is carried out in case of a complicated wound. In general, gastric ulcer disease by surgery is used in very few cases. Because modern medicine has proven that it is possible to achieve the expected

result in the treatment of the disease in a conservative way. The doctors working at RUSTAMOV'S clinic, who have many years of experience, make a great contribution to the treatment of patients suffering from ulcer disease and improving their quality of life.

Conclusion: It is important for the patient to follow a diet and not eat forbidden foods. Long walks in the open air, treatment in sanatoriums are also useful. According to the doctor's recommendation, a continuous course of antisecretory drugs can be prescribed

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